
Research Article

***Callicarpa ogasawarensis*, a replacement name for *C. boninensis* Sugai & Setsuko (Lamiaceae)**

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Abstract: A new name, *Callicarpa ogasawarensis* R.Kr.Singh, is proposed here as a replacement for the illegitimate name *C. boninensis* Sugai & Setsuko, which is a later homonym of *C. boninensis* Hayata (Lamiaceae).

Keywords: Endemic, Illegitimate name, Japan, Later homonym, Ogasawara Islands

Introduction

The genus *Callicarpa* L. comprises about 165 species, distributed from temperate to tropical regions of Australia, Central America, East Asia, the Indian subcontinent, Madagascar, North America, the Pacific Islands and Southeast Asia (POWO, 2026). In Japan, the genus is represented by 16 species, including natural hybrids (Sugai et al., 2025; POWO, 2026). The name *Callicarpa boninensis* Sugai & Setsuko was recently published for a species endemic to the Ogasawara Islands, Japan. However, this name is illegitimate because it is a later homonym of *C. boninensis* Hayata, published earlier for a different taxon, in accordance with Article 53.1 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2025). To resolve this nomenclatural conflict, the replacement name *C. ogasawarensis* is proposed here.

Nomenclature

Callicarpa ogasawarensis R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Callicarpa boninensis* Sugai & Setsuko, *Phytotaxa* 736(1): 2. 2025, *nom. illeg., non* Hayata, *J. Coll. Sci. Imp. Univ. Tokyo* 30(1): 218. 1911.

Holotype: Japan, Tokyo Metropolis, Ogasawara Islands, Hahajima Island, Sekimon, 248 m, 18 July 2023, K. Hayama (MAK472470).

Distribution: Endemic to Ogasawara Islands, Japan.

Etymology: Named after Ogasawara Islands, Japan.

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